

Improvement of voltage profile for large scale power system using soft computing approach

Muhammad Abdillah¹, Herlambang Setiadi², Danang Sulisty³

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Pertamina, Indonesia

²Department of Engineering, Faculty of Vocational Studies, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia

³PT. Pakoakuina, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 21, 2019

Revised Nov 17, 2019

Accepted Nov 30, 2019

Keywords:

JAMALI 500 kV

Power loss

Reactive power

Shunt capacitor

ABSTRACT

In modern power system operation, control, and planning, reactive power as part of power system component is very important in order to supply electrical load such as an electric motor. However, the reactive current that flows from the generator to load demand can cause voltage drop and active power loss. Hence, it is essential to install a compensating device such as a shunt capacitor close to the load bus to improve the voltage profile and decrease the total power loss of transmission line system. This paper presents the application of a genetic algorithm (GA), particle swarm optimization (PSO), and artificial bee colony (ABC) to obtain the optimal size of the shunt capacitor where those capacitors are located on the critical bus. The effectiveness of the proposed technique is examined by utilizing Java-Madura-Bali (JAMALI) 500 kV power system grid as the test system. From the simulation results, the PSO and ABC algorithms are providing satisfactory results in obtaining the capacitor size and can reduce the total power loss of around 15.873 MW. Moreover, a different result is showed by the GA approach where the power loss in the JAMALI 500kV power grid can be compressed only up to 15.54 MW or 11.38% from the power system operation without a shunt capacitor. The three soft computing techniques could also maintain the voltage profile within 1.05 p.u and 0.95 p.u.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Herlambang Setiadi,

Department of Engineering, Faculty of Vocational Studies,

Universitas Airlangga,

Campus B UNAIR, 65 Srikana St., 60286, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Email: herlambang.setiadi@vokasi.unair.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

In electric power systems, transmission lines play a key role to distribute electrical energy from power plants to consumers. Electrical energy distributed by transmission lines consists of active and reactive powers. In fact, the place of electric power plants is spatially isolated from the consumer. This causes an enormous challenge in electricity transportation over a long distance which could affect the level of performance and security of the system. Reactive power is not only generated by the impedance of a large power system network but also produced by electrical devices such as motor, transformer and other power electronic components. Hence, this power may have a great impact on the system performance. Reactive power consumed by all electrical loads is supplied by generation units when there are no sources of reactive power on electrical load from the transmission line system. The current flowing in the transmission lines increases due to reactive power on electrical load increases which initiates large reactive current flowing in

the transmission lines. A large amount of reactive currents flowing in the transmission line causes decreasing in the power factor, increasing network loss and voltage drop. Therefore, the desired voltage profile on the consumer side becomes inappropriate. To overcome this problem, the shunt capacitor is an important device to install in the transmission line as reactive power compensation [1]. An appropriate planning methodology should be conducted for merging shunt capacitors as reactive power compensation into a power system network in order to get its benefit. The installation of these compensating devices at non-appropriate areas with incorrect sizing leads to negative consequences such as an increase in power loss and voltage instability. There were classical approaches for solving reactive power problems such as mixed-integer programming, non-linear programming, linear programming and quadratic programming [2-4]. Nevertheless, these approaches have some issues in solving the objective functions that were trapped in local minima. To tackle the inherent limitations of these solution methods, some simplification has been used to all these practices. Divergence and local minimum could emerge due the simplification of the problems. Additionally, the conventional method is consuming computation burden time for finding the solution.

Nowadays, many new soft computing methods have been used for solving optimization problems and widely employed to handle various problems in engineering fields. Smart computation can be divided into three categories: first categories is biologically inspired approaches such as grey wolf optimization, fruit fly algorithm and social spider algorithm. Second categories is physically inspired such as simulated annealing algorithm, and lastly social inspired such as imperialist competitive algorithm, and tabu search algorithm [5]. There are a number of researches that utilizing soft computing based on biological inspired approaches to solve optimization problems such as genetic algorithm (GA) to determine the optimal generator output [6], ant colony optimization (ACO) for reactive power management [7], differential evolution (DE) algorithm to solve non-convex and high non-linear problems [8, 9], particle swarm optimization (PSO) for reactive power dispatch [10], biogeography based optimization (BBO) for optimal VAR control [11], harmony search algorithm (HSA) for reactive dispatch [12], hybrid tabu search algorithm (TS) and simulated annealing algorithm (SA) for optimal reactive power problem [13], teaching learning based optimization algorithm (TLBO) for reactive power planning [14], group search optimization (GSO) for power and emission dispatch [15], honey bee mating optimization (HBMO) for power loss minimization [16], gravitational search algorithm (GSA) to determine the optimal FACTS for reactive power planning [17], artificial bee colony algorithm (ABC) for reactive power flow [18], cuckoo optimization algorithm (COA) [19] and artificial immune system (AIS) [20] for distribution network reconfiguration problem.

Moreover, the application of soft computing in optimizing the size of the shunt capacitor has been investigated by many researches as reactive power compensation as reported in [21]. In [21] the bacterial foraging algorithm is used to locate as well as sizing the capacity of the capacitor in the radial distribution system. The application of fuzzy logic for placement of the capacitor in the radial distribution system is reported in [22]. Moreover, the application of a whale optimization algorithm for the siting of capacitors in the radial distribution network is reported in [23]. In this paper, three computing methods i.e GA, PSO and ABC are employed to find the optimal size of the shunt capacitor as reactive power compensation. The GA, PSO, and ABC are used in this study because they have been popular in academia and industry because of its ability to effectively solve highly non-linear problems. Some benefits of GA are defined as follow: a) it has the aptitude to elude being trapped in local optimal due to GA search parallel from a population of points unlike traditional and other optimization methods, which search from a single point and affect the methods to trapped on local optima, b) it uses probabilistic preference rules rather than deterministic ones, c) the potential solution parameters are encoded to chromosome rather than the parameters themselves, d) the fitness score obtained from objective functions is utilized without other derivative or auxiliary information. Meanwhile, the GA has drawbacks due to it has many parameters that should be set appropriately and has expensive computational cost. Furthermore, the PSO method has attracted much attention from researcher communities due to it has few parameters to adjust, it can be simple to implement, it can converge fast, it doesn't need a crossover and mutate, it has higher probability and efficiency in finding global optima, and it has short computational time. Those are the advantages of PSO compared to GA. While the usage of ABC due to ABC has the same effectiveness (finding the true global optimal solution) as the PSO. Both PSO and ABC are having significantly better computational efficiency (fewer function evaluations) than GA.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The objective function is to minimize the active power loss (P_{loss}) of the transmission line. Reactive power compensation is obtained by installing the shunt capacitor on Java-Madura-Bali (JAMALI) 500 kV power system grid to reduce the losses of P_{loss} . The active power loss (P_{loss}) can be calculated using (1).

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_l} g_k [(t_k V_i)^2 + V_j^2 - 2t_k V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij}] \quad (1)$$

In (1), N_l is the number of transmission lines, g_k is conductance of branch k between i and j , t_k is the tap ratio of transformer k , V_i is the voltage magnitude at bus i , and θ_{ij} is the difference of voltage angle between buses i and j , respectively. By obtaining the minimum objective function, the determination of the size of the shunt capacitor as reactive power compensation is essential. Furthermore, the equality constraint in optimal power flow can be described in (2) and (3).

$$P_{g_i} - P_{d_i} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{N_{bus}} V_j (G_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij}) = 0, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{pv} + N_{pq} \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{g_i} - Q_{d_i} + Q_{c_i} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{N_{bus}} V_j (G_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij}) = 0, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{pq} \quad (3)$$

where N_{pv} and N_{pq} are the number of generators and load buses, respectively. While the inequality constraint of power flow can be calculated using (4), (5), (6) and (7).

$$P_{g,slack}^{\min} \leq P_{gen,slack} \leq P_{g,slack}^{\max} \quad (4)$$

$$V_{L_i}^{\min} \leq V_{L_i} \leq V_{L_i}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{pq} \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{g_i}^{\min} \leq Q_{g_i} \leq Q_{g_i}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{gen} \quad (6)$$

$$S_{line} \leq S_{line}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{line} \quad (7)$$

The inequality constraint as the control variable can be described in (8), (9), and (10):

$$V_{gen_i}^{\min} \leq V_{gen_i} \leq V_{gen_i}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{pv} \quad (8)$$

$$t_{k_i}^{\min} \leq t_{k_i} \leq t_{k_i}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{tf} \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{c_i}^{\min} \leq Q_{c_i} \leq Q_{c_i}^{\max}, \text{ for } i=1, \dots, N_{comp} \quad (10)$$

where N_{tf} and N_{comp} are the number of tap transformer and reactive compensating devices, respectively.

3. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

3.1. Genetic algorithm (GA)

The genetic algorithm (GA) is a soft computing method inspired by the theory of gen in biological sciences [6] where introduced by John Holland in 1970. Chromosome variation will affect the reproduction rate and level of ability of the organism to survive. The control parameters of GA consist of population size, crossover, and mutation. Basically, there are four conditions that affect the evaluation process of GA:

- Organism's ability to reproduce.
- The existence of populations of organisms that can perform reproduction.
- The diversity of organisms within a population.
- Different inability to survive.

Stronger individuals would have the level of survival and reproduction rates are higher when compared to an individual who is not strong. At a certain time (generation), the overall population will contain more fit organ-isms. Processing steps of Genetic Algorithm are defined as follow:

- Encoding problem solution into a set of chromosome structures
- GA initialized to a population with a few N chromosomes
- Each chromosome will be encoded into an individual with a specific fitness value.

- Selecting individuals with the best fitness value. The method used is different, for example by using the method roulette wheel.
- To generate a new population, it is necessary to use the genetic
 - a. Cross Over: generate new offspring by replacing some of the information from the parent chromosomes that are crossed by.
 - b. Mutation: create new individuals by modifying one or more genes in the chromosome.

3.2. Particle swarm optimization

The second optimization approach employed in this paper is particle swarm optimization (PSO) proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart in 1995 [10] where this algorithm mimics the behavior of bird flocking. This algorithm is a population-based search approach where each individual in a population is presented as a particle. Each particle in a swarm flies around in a multi-dimensional search space by memorizing its own experience and the experience of neighboring particles [10]. Furthermore, the flowchart of PSO is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of PSO

The velocity of a particle to move can be evaluated using information from: (i) the present velocity, (ii) the distance between the starting position with the best position that has been found. Based on the concept of PSO, the mathematical representation of particle velocity and particle position can be expressed using (11) and (12),

$$v_i^{k+1} = v_i + c_1 r_1 (P_{best_i} - x_i^k) + c_2 r_2 (G_{best} - x_i^k) \quad (11)$$

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i + v_i^{k+1} \quad (12)$$

in (11) and (12), w is inertia weight, c is the speed constant, the *rand* is a uniform random value in the range [0, 1], P_{best} is the best position of the i -th particle and G_{best} is the best position of all P_{best} .

3.3. Artificial bee colony

The third optimization method utilized in this study is an artificial bee colony algorithm introduced by Karaboga [18] where this algorithm mimics the behavior of bees in searching for the food. In the ABC algorithm, the colonies of artificial bees are classified into three categories of bees i.e the employed bees, the onlooker bees, and the scout bees. The employed bees seek the new food source that never prior to being visited, while the onlooker bees that are waiting in the dance area are to make decisions in the preference of food sources site. The third bees are the scout bees that are doing random searching for the food sources. Noted that only one employed bee exists for each food source. Thus, it could be emphasized that the number of food sources around the nest equals the set of employed bees in the colony. When the employed bees run out of their food sources, then, they become the scout bees [18]. The location of a food source denotes a potential solution to the optimization issue. The number of food sources called the nectar corresponds to the quality (fitness) of the associated solution. Furthermore, the main steps of ABC are described below:

- Initialize the location for food source.
- Devolve the employed bees onto their food sources and specify the number of their nectars. A new food source of each employed bee is described as (13). The new solution is compared to the solution x_{ij} after the result in v_{ij} and the employed bee exploits the better source.

$$v_{ij} = x_{ij} + \varphi_{ij}(x_{ij} - x_{kj}) \quad (13)$$

- Devolve the onlooker bees towards the food sources and specify the number of their nectars. In this step, the probability is employed by an onlooker bee to pick a food source and yields a new source in the location of the chosen food source. While for the employed bee, the preferred food source is defined to be exploited by (14).

$$P_i = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{SN} fit_i} \quad (14)$$

- Determine the food source to be forsaken and allocate its employed bee as a scout for finding the new food sources based on a random search by (15).

$$x_i^j = x_{min}^j + rand[0,1](x_{max}^j - x_{min}^j) \quad (15)$$

- Memorize the best food source found so far.
- Go steps 2-until the termination criteria are satisfied.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this paper, the test system is Java-Madura-Bali (JAMALI) 500kV power grid as depicted in Figure 2. The data of the JAMALI 500kV power grid is taken from [24]. Simulation is conducted by using a MATLAB software environment. Furthermore, the appropriate control parameter plays key role in the computation techniques and is very sensitive problem of finding a good solution for the soft computing technique. The parameters of soft computing approaches used for the simulations are defined as follow:

GA parameters:

N_{Gen} =Dimension of problem; Crossover probability = 0.8; Population siz = 50;
Mutation probability = 0.05; Maximum generations = 150

PSO parameters:

$N_{Variabel}$ = Dimension of problem; Social parameter (C2) = 0.9; Weight (w)= 0.9;
Cognitive parameter (C1) =1.5; Population size = 50; Maximum iterations = 150;

ABC parameters:

Dimension (D) = Dimension of problem; FoodNumber = NP/2; limit = FoodNumber*D;
colony size (NP) = 50; Maximum cycles = 150;

The dimension search space (Dim) of each algorithm depends on the number of compensating devices corresponding to the number of bus systems that have voltage value (p.u) lower than voltage reference standard around -5% of its nominal value.

Figure 2. Single line diagram of JAMALI 500 kV transmission system [25]

The evaluation of fitness for each population of the GA, PSO, and ABC algorithms is frequently conducted in one iteration. The convergence characteristic of three soft computing techniques is compared to the number of fitness evaluations due to the fitness evaluation is consuming the optimization process time. The convergence behavior of all soft computing approaches is depicted in Figure 3. Figure 3 illustrates that all soft computing approaches obtained satisfactory performances to reach their convergence values for the chosen parameters. The convergence characteristics of GA are faster than ABC but may not investigate deeply for potential candidates as found by ABC. While PSO towards convergence value quickly and explores a good potential solution rather than other soft computing methods. Table 1 shows the comparison of total loss before and after the installing of capacitors from each of these methods. The results obtained are that the GA method can reduce the transmission line losses 11.38%. A better result is obtained by using PSO and ABC algorithm

with a percentage decrease of 11.63%. While Table 2 depicts the capacity of capacitors installed on each of the critical buses. The comparison of the voltage level on each result is depicted in Figure 4. It is found that after the system is compensated, the voltage drops decrease in order to obtain better performance of voltage.

Figure 3. Convergence characteristics of algorithms

Figure 4. Comparison of voltages level

Table 1. Comparison of total active power loss

		Before	GA	PSO	ABC
Total Loss	(MW)	136.539	120.999	120.666	120.666
The difference of total loss	(MW)	-	15.54	15.873	15.873
	%	-	11.38	11.63	11.63

Table 2. Optimization of shunt capacitor's size

Unit	Bus	Compensation	Compensation	Compensation
		GA (MVAR)	PSO (MVAR)	ABC (MVAR)
1	13	370.451	400	400
2	14	376.878	400	400
3	19	399.272	248.244	248.245
4	20	386.468	400	400
5	21	369.731	400	400
Total	1902.8	1848.244	1848.245	

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the use of three different soft computing techniques to overcome the reactive power compensation issue in the transmission system has been investigated. From the simulation result, it is shown that the GA method to reach convergence on the 20th iteration, PSO on the 3rd iteration and ABC on the 23rd iteration. The ABC dan PSO algorithms can reduce the total active power loss by 15.873 MW, from 136.539 MW to 120.666 MW. These results obtained are better than the GA approach where it only can reduce by 15.54 MW, from 136.539 MW to 120.999 MW. From all the simulation results, the PSO algorithm is very superior rather than the other methods in the viewpoint of the selected set of parameters to tackle the reactive power compensation issue in the transmission system.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the anonymous reviewers for their precious comments and suggestions for the improvement of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Dixit, *et al.*, "Optimal Integration of Shunt Capacitor Banks in Distribution Networks for Assessment of Techno-Economic Asset," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 71, pp. 331-345, Oct 2018.
- [2] D. S. Kirschen, *et al.*, "MW/Voltage Control in Linear Programming Based Optimal Power Flow," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 481–489, May 1988.
- [3] N. Grudin, "Reactive power optimization using successive quadratic programming method," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 1219-1225, Nov 1998.
- [4] K. Aoki, M. Fan and A. Nishikori, "Optimal VAR planning by approximation method for recursive mixed-integer linear programming," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1741-1747, Nov 1988.
- [5] H. Setiadi, *et al.*, "Power System Design using Firefly Algorithm for Dynamic Stability Enhancement," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 1, no.3, pp. 446-455, Mar 2016.
- [6] A. G. Bakirtzis, P. N. Biskas, C. E. Zoumas and V. Petridis, "Optimal power flow by enhanced genetic algorithm," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 229-236, May 2002.
- [7] A. Ketabi, *et al.*, "Application of The Ant Colony Search Algorithm to Reactive Power Pricing in an Open Electricity Market," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 32, pp. 622-628, July 2010.
- [8] A. A. Abou El Ela, *et al.*, "Optimal Power Flow using Differential Evolution Algorithm," *Electr. Power Syst Res.*, vol. 80, no. 7, pp. 878-885, July 2010.
- [9] N. H. Awada, *et al.*, "An Efficient Differential Evolution Algorithm for Stochastic OPF Based Active-Reactive Power Dispatch Problem Considering Renewable Generators," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 76, pp. 445-458, 2019.
- [10] M. R. Monteiro, *et al.*, "Particle Swarm Optimization Applied to Reactive Power Dispatch Considering Renewable Generation," *Decision Making Applications in Modern Power Systems*, United Kingdom: Academic Press, pp. 247-267, 2020.
- [11] P. K. Roy, *et al.*, "Optimal VAR Control for Improvements in Voltage Profiles and For Real Power Loss Minimization using Biogeography Based Optimization," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 830-838, December 2012.
- [12] A. H. Khazali, *et al.*, "Optimal Reactive Power Dispatch Based on Harmony Search Algorithm," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 684-692, Mar 2011.
- [13] K. Lenin, *et al.*, "Hybrid Tabu Search-Simulated Annealing Method to Solve Optimal Reactive Power Problem," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 82, pp. 87-91, November 2016.
- [14] B. Bhattacharyya, *et al.*, "Teaching Learning Based Optimization Algorithm for Reactive Power Planning," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 81, pp. 248-253, Oct 2016.
- [15] N. Daryani, *et al.*, "Multi-Objective Power and Emission Dispatch using Modified Group Search Optimization Method," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 319-328, Sep 2018.
- [16] E. A. Farsani, "Loss Minimization in Distribution Systems Based on LMP Calculation using Honey Bee Mating Optimization and Point Estimate Method," *Energy*, vol. 140, pp. 1-9, Dec 2017.
- [17] B. Bhattacharyya, *et al.*, "Reactive Power Planning with FACTS Devices using Gravitational Search Algorithm," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 865-871, Sep 2015.

- [18] K. Ayan, *et al.*, "Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm Solution for Optimal Reactive Power Flow," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 12, no. 5 pp. 1477-1482, May 2012.
- [19] T. Thanh Nguyen, *et al.*, "An Improved Cuckoo Search Algorithm for The Problem of Electric Distribution Network Reconfiguration," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 84, pp. 1-8, Nov 2019.
- [20] S. S. F. Souza, *et al.*, "Artificial Immune Algorithm Applied to Distribution System Reconfiguration with Variable Demand," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 82, pp. 561-568, Nov 2016.
- [21] K. R. Devabalaji, *et al.*, "Optimal Location and Sizing of Capacitor Placement in Radial Distribution System using Bacterial Foraging Optimization Algorithm," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 71, pp. 383-390, Oct 2015.
- [22] S. K. Bhattacharya, *et al.*, "A New Fuzzy Based Solution of The Capacitor Placement Problem in Radial Distribution System," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 4207-4212, Apr 2009.
- [23] D. B. Prakash, *et al.*, "Optimal Siting of Capacitors in Radial Distribution Network using Whale Optimization Algorithm," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 499-509, Dec 2017.
- [24] M. A. Juningtijastuti, *et al.*, "Optimal Sizing of Static Var Compensators (SVCs) for Reducing Power Losses in 500 kV JAMALI Grid Power System using Bacteria Foraging Algorithm (BFA)," *Proceeding of National Seminar of Mathematics*, University of Indonesia, 2010.
- [25] D. Lastomo, Widodo and H. Setiadi, "Optimal Power Flow using Fuzzy-Firefly Algorithm," *2018 5th International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computer Science and Informatics (EECSI)*, Malang, Indonesia, pp. 210-215, 2018.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Muhammad Abdillah was born in Pasuruan. He received Sarjana Teknik (equivalent to B.Eng.), and Magister Teknik (equivalent to M.Eng.) degrees from Department of Electrical Engineering, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ITS), Surabaya, Indonesia in 2009 and 2013, respectively. He obtained Dr. Eng. degree from Graduate School of Engineering, Hiroshima University, Japan in 2017. He is currently working as lecturer at Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Pertamina, Jakarta, Indonesia. As author and co-author, he had published 70 scientific papers in different journals and conferences. He was a member of IEEE, IAENG and IEEEE. His research interests are power system operation and control, power system optimization, robust power system security, power system stability, intelligent control and system, and artificial intelligences (optimization, machine learning, and deep learning).

Herlambang Setiadi was born in Sidoarjo, in November 1990. He received a Bachelor degree from Sepuluh Nopember Institute of Technology (Surabaya, Indonesia) majors in Power System Engineering in 2014. Then a Master degree from Liverpool John Moores University (Liverpool, United Kingdom), majors in Electrical Power and Control Engineering in 2015. Furthermore, he received his Doctoral degree from The University of Queensland, majors in Electrical Engineering in 2019. Currently, he is a lecturer at the Department of Engineering, Universitas Airlangga. His research interests include small signal stability in power systems, renewable energy integration, control system engineering and metaheuristic algorithms. The author can be contacted at [herlambang.setiadi @vokasi.unair.ac.id](mailto:herlambang.setiadi@vokasi.unair.ac.id).

Danang Sulisty was born in Madiun. He received Sarjana Teknik (equivalent to B.Eng.) from Department of Electrical Engineering, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (Surabaya, Indonesia) majors in Power System Engineering in 2010. During his bachelor studied period, he had involved in the research area related to artificial intelligence that was applied to power system optimization. He is currently working as process engineer at PT. Pakoakuina, Jakarta, Indonesia.